

A STUDY OF SELF CONCEPT OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

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Abstract:

The study aimed to assessment the self concept of higher secondary students. For the present investigation a sample of 250 higher secondary students from the Vellore District are selected by the method of Random sampling technique. The data so collected was analyzed using mean, SD, t-test and F-test. The results reveal that respect to the gender, locality of school, type of management, medium of instruction, parental occupation, parental qualification and type of family have average level of self concept towards higher secondary students and further it shows that there is significant difference between the types of management of higher secondary students towards self concept.

Introduction:

Education is the key to all processes of development especially human development. Catalytic action of education in this complex and dynamic growth process needs to be planned meticulously and executed with great sensitivity. Education is fundamental to all-round development of human potential-material and spiritual. It refines sensitivities and perceptions that contribute to national cohesion, a scientific temper and independence of mind and spirit thus furthering to goal of socialism, secularism and democracy enshrined in our constitution.

Education is the main tool in the hands of man through which he enables himself to meet the various challenges of the life. It is a unique feature of human society which enables the human beings, not only to distinguish between the civilized and uncivilized, but also help them to achieve what otherwise remains unachieved. India has witnessed phenomenal development in education since independence. The overall literacy rate has gone up significantly during this period. It is the teacher with sufficient degree of mental health who can maintain the twin requisites of teaching-learning situations, healthy interactions in the classroom and healthy participation by students in lessons.

Self Concept:

Self-concept is often defined not so much in terms of what we think of ourselves as in terms of what we think, others think of us. Self-concept works like a mirror; we look at other people to see ourselves. If we think they think we are valuable, we think we are valuable; if we think they think we are deficient, we think we are deficient. Obviously, this definition has direct implications for teachers. Teachers who send clear, positive messages to their students are likely to enhance student's self-concepts, while teachers who berate their students may diminish their sense of self-worth. Teachers' criticism can damage students' self-concepts.

Self-concept theorists promote self-concept as the most important and focal object within the experience of each individual because of its primacy, centrality, continuity and ubiquity in all aspects of behavior. Bakadorova et al (2009) was prompted to acknowledge that only man has the ability to objectify himself, to stand apart from himself and consider what he is and what he would like to do and become. Nguyen, Hong T.; Scott, Amy N. (2008). Sees man as transcending all other forms of living beings since only he is the being actually aware of it. Huang, Chiungjung, (2011). Also claims self awareness as the fundamental characteristics and evolutionary novelty of Homo sapiens. This self awareness places considerable implications on human experiences since it involves a search for the meaning of life itself. Man's conception of himself influences his choice of behaviours and his expectations from life.

According to Hattie (1992), Self-concept has typically been defined in terms of the cognitive appraisal one makes of the expectations, descriptions, and prescriptions that one holds about one's self. Huit (1998) also added that, self-concept is a person's perceptions of his or her own strengths and weaknesses. There are three aspects of self-concept which are; self-image (of what the person is), ideal self (what the person wants to be), and self-esteem (what the person feels about the discrepancy between what she/he is and what she/he would like to be) (Lawrence 1996).

Statement of the Problem:

The problem chosen for the study may be stated as "A Study of self concept of higher secondary students".

Sample of the Study:

Normative survey method is adopted for the present study. For the present investigation a sample of 250 higher secondary students from the Vellore District are selected by the method of random sampling.

Statistical Techniques Used:

The investigator used the statistical techniques, Mean, Standard Deviation 't' test and 'F' test to accept or reject hypotheses

Operational Definitions of Key Term Used:

Self-concept Self- Concept, in the present study, means the individual’s view of himself. Self-concept can be defined as the mental image one has of oneself. It is the individual’s evaluation of various aspects of the self and his ideas about himself. In simple terms, self-concept is the concept of one’s own self.

Tool Used In the Present Study:

Self Concept by Dr. (Miss) Mukta Rani Restogi, National Psychological. New Delhi.

Description of the Tool:

Self-concept can be described as the mental image one has of oneself. This image of course may be composed of a host of attributes. There are many attributes that define our images of ourselves, physical appearance, wit, charm, religiousness, ethnicity, sociability, success, etc. The scoring is based on 5,4,3,2 and 1.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find out the level of self concept of higher secondary students.
- ✓ To find out the difference if any between the following higher secondary students in respect of their self concept
 - Gender : Male/ Female
 - Locality of School : Rural / Urban
 - Type of Management : Government / Private / Aided
 - Medium of Institution : English / Tamil
 - Parental Occupation : Educated / Uneducated
 - Type of Family : Nuclear / Joint
 - Father Qualification : Illiterate / school Education / College Education

Hypotheses of the Study:

- ✓ The self concept of higher secondary students is high
- ✓ There is no significant difference between the following sub-samples with respect to the self concept of higher secondary students
 - Gender : Male/ Female
 - Locality of School : Rural / Urban
 - Type of Management : Government / Private / Aided
 - Medium of Institution : English / Tamil
 - Parental Occupation : Educated / Uneducated
 - Type of Family : Nuclear / Joint
 - Father Qualification : Illiterate / school Education / College Education

Descriptive Analysis:

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Self Concept of Higher Secondary Students

Categories	Sub Samples	N	Mean	SD	Level
Entire Sample		250	82.56	25.48	Avg
Gender	Male	136	82.15	26.56	Avg
	Female	114	82.56	25.48	Avg
Locality of School	Rural	104	80.91	24.94	Avg
	Urban	146	83.73	25.87	Avg
Type of Management	Government	78	80.03	28.50	Avg
	Private	97	87.70	24.17	Avg
	Aided	75	78.54	22.87	Avg
Medium of Instruction	English	128	83.35	26.96	Avg
	Tamil	122	81.72	23.90	Avg
Parental Occupation	Employed	145	83.36	26.86	Avg
	Unemployed	105	81.45	23.52	Avg
Parental Qualification	Illiterate	95	80.95	27.89	Avg
	School Education	104	85.43	23.34	Avg
	College Education	51	79.70	20.45	Avg
Type of Family	Nuclear	152	82.27	26.16	Avg
	Joint	118	82.88	24.79	Avg

In this study, based on normal curve of higher secondary students secured scores in between 57.08 to 108.04 (-1σ to $+1\sigma$) are classified as having average level of achievement motivation. In the table 1 shows the self concept mean and standard deviation values. The calculated mean values are less than 57.08 and more than 108.04. Therefore, it is found that the higher secondary students irrespective of their gender, locality of school, type of management, medium of instruction, parental occupation, parental qualification and type of family have average level of self concept.

Differential Analysis for Self Concept – Higher Secondary Students:

Table 2: ‘t’ Test Values For Self concept Scores – Higher Secondary Students – Based on Gender

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	S.D	‘t’ Value
Male	136	82.15	26.56	0.277 ^{NS}
Female	114	83.05	24.23	

Table 2 further reveals the mean, standard deviation and ‘t’ values of male and female higher secondary students on self concept. The calculated ‘t’ value is 0.277, which is lower than the table value of 1.97 to be significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the research hypothesis is rejected and null hypothesis is accepted. Further it is found that the male and female higher secondary students do not differ significantly in their self concept.

Table 3: ‘t’ Test Values For Self Concept Scores –Higher Secondary Students – Based on Locality of School

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	S.D	‘t’ Value
Rural	104	80.91	24.94	0.864 ^{NS}
Urban	146	83.73	25.87	

Table 3 further reveals the mean, standard deviation and ‘t’ values of rural and urban higher secondary students on self concept. The calculated ‘t’ value is 0.864, which is lower than the table value of 1.97 to be significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the research hypothesis is rejected and null hypothesis is accepted. Further it is found that the rural and urban higher secondary students do not differ significantly in their self concept.

Table 4: ‘F’ Test Values for Self Concept Scores – Higher Secondary Students – Based on Type of Management

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	‘F’ Value
Between Groups	4267.675	2133.837	2	3.348 ^S
Within Groups	157425.801	637.351	247	
Total	161693.476		249	

Table 4 the calculated ‘F’ value is 3.348, which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their self concept of higher secondary students.

Table 5: ‘t’ Test Values For Self Concept Scores –Higher Secondary Students – Based on Medium of Instruction

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	S.D	‘t’ Value
English	128	83.35	26.96	0.063 ^{NS}
Tamil	122	81.72	23.90	

Table 5 further reveals the mean, standard deviation and ‘t’ values of English and Tamil higher secondary students on self concept. The calculated ‘t’ value is 0.063, which is lower than the table value of 1.97 to be significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the research hypothesis is rejected and null hypothesis is accepted. Further it is found that the English medium and Tamil medium higher secondary students do not differ significantly in their self concept.

Table 6: ‘t’ Test Values For Self Concept Scores –Higher Secondary Students – Based on Parental Occupation

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	S.D	‘t’ Value
Employed	145	83.36	26.86	0.584 ^{NS}
Unemployed	105	81.45	23.52	

Table 6 further reveals the mean, standard deviation and ‘t’ values of whose parental occupation employed and unemployed of higher secondary students on self concept. The calculated ‘t’ value is 0.584, which is lower than the table value of 1.97 to be significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the research hypothesis is rejected and null hypothesis is accepted. Further it is found that the parental occupation employed and unemployed occupation of higher secondary students do not differ significantly in their self concept.

Table 7: ‘F’ Test Values for Self Concept Scores –Higher Secondary Students – Based on Parental Qualification

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	‘F’ Value
Between Groups	1517.527	758.764	2	1.170 ^{NS}
Within Groups	160175.949	648.486	247	
Total	161693.476		249	

Table 7, the calculated ‘F’ value is 1.170, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of parental qualification with respect to their self concept of higher secondary students.

Table 8: ‘t’ Test Values For Self Concept Scores –Higher Secondary Students – Based on Type of Family

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	S.D	‘t’ Value
Nuclear	132	82.88	24.79	0.191 ^{NS}
Joint	118	82.27	26.16	

Table 8 further reveals the mean, standard deviation and 't' values of whose type of family nuclear and joint of higher secondary students on mental health. The calculated 't' value is 0.191, which is lower than the table value of 1.97 to be significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the research hypothesis is rejected and null hypothesis is accepted. Further it is found that the type of family nuclear and joint of higher secondary students do not differ significantly in their self concept.

Major Findings of the Study:

- ✓ It is found that the higher secondary students irrespective of their gender, locality of school, type of management, medium of instruction, parental occupation, parental qualification and type of family have average level of self concept.
- ✓ It is found that the male and female higher secondary students do not differ significantly in their self concept.
- ✓ It is found that the rural and urban higher secondary students do not differ significantly in their self concept.
- ✓ It is found that there is a significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their self concept of higher secondary students.
- ✓ It is found that the English medium and Tamil medium higher secondary students do not differ significantly in their self concept.
- ✓ It is found that whose parental occupation employed and unemployed occupation of higher secondary students do not differ significantly in their self concept.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among sub samples of parental qualification with respect to their self concept of higher secondary students.
- ✓ It is found that the type of family nuclear and joint of higher secondary students do not differ significantly in their self concept.

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